

Let There be Light

EOS:
*A demonstrator for
next-generation
neutrino detection*

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NuPhys 2026

Innovative neutrino detection

Combine two well-tested methods for neutrino detection, for enhanced precision:

Cherenkov light

- Emitted with a unique topology that preserves directional information
- Particle-dependent threshold

Scintillation light

- Extremely high light yield: high efficiency for detection
- Particle-dependent response offers particle identification

The whole is greater than the sum of the parts

The ratio of the two signals provides additional information on the type of particle interacting:
Improved background rejection for precision measurements

Challenging technical goal: preserve directional Cherenkov signature against more abundant scintillation yield

THEIA

- **Hybrid Cherenkov/ scintillation detector**
- **Multi-messenger astrophysics**
- **Probe the fundamental nature of matter: CPV and Majorana ν**
- **Technological developments have evolved from bench-top to fully integrated demonstrators**
- ***Exciting physics to come!***

Enabling technology

We focus our studies on three technologies that optimize hybrid Cherenkov/scintillation detection:

1. Novel targets, such as water-based liquid scintillator (WbLS). Enhances Cherenkov detection by “dialling down” or otherwise modifying the scintillation signal

2. Large-Area Picosecond Photon Detectors (LAPPDs). Fast-timing discrimination for vertex resolution and Cherenkov/scintillation separation

3. Dichroicons (“chromatic quantum sensing”). Cherenkov/scintillation separation via spectral sorting

We seek to characterize behavior, understand and model performance at a microphysical level, and use results to extrapolate performance to kton scales.

Technical development

(Wb) SCINTILLATOR

WbLS R&D
(BNL, Mainz)

WbLS tuning
(LBNL)

Slow LS
(Oxford, Mainz)

Attenuation
(UC.B, LLNL, Davis)

Hadron LY
(LBNL)

Filtration
(Davis)

[Slide from A. Mastbaum]

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FAST DETECTORS

LAPPD R&D (Iowa State, LBNL)	Fast PMTS (Penn, LBNL)

[Slide from A. Mastbaum]

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INTEGRATED

CHES
(LBNL)

[Slide from A. Mastbaum]

The path to THEIA

ANNIE: 365 kg

High-energy event reconstruction,
neutrino detection

Eos: 20 ton

Low-energy event reconstruction,
model validation

Building on a broad program of
bench-top scale development

BUTTON: 30 ton

Underground
deployment, low
bkg verification

BNL: 1- and 30-ton

Deployment, purification,
recirculation, transparency

NuDot: 1 ton

Isotope loading,
NLDBD topology

Eos (Darwin)

*Funded by NNSA,
DNN R&D
FY22-27*

Let There be Light

EOS: performance demonstrator

A flexible, multi-ton scale integrated testbed to demonstrate the performance of novel technology

Novelty / technology:

- 4-ton acrylic inner vessel — water, WbLS, novel LS
- High coverage (50%, 242 PMTs)
- Ultra-fast photon detectors — RI4688-100, 900ps FWHM
- “Quantum chromatic sorting”: dichroicons for spectrally sensitive photon detection
- Deployable sources (β , γ , tagged- γ , AmBe, PuBe, directional) for studies of vertex, energy, direction reconstruction & PID
- AI/ML-based analysis techniques
- 36-fiber light injection system for optical calibration

Sited on UC Berkeley campus, in Nuclear Engineering department

*Designed for flexible upgrade paths & to be redeployed at a neutrino source
→ demonstrate viability of future applications*

EOS concept paper published: *JINST* 18 P02009 (2023),
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/18/02/P02009>

EOS detector design

- Aggressive 3-year duration to go from concept sketch to first results
 - FY22: detector design and large-scale procurements
 - FY23: procurement and installation
 - FY24: Installation, commissioning and data taking
- Program goals
 - Study the impact of integrated novel technology for hybrid event reconstruction
 - Explore water-based liquid scintillator performance as $f(\%LS)$
 - Study impact of slow / fast LS
 - Evaluate dichroicon performance
 - Validate model predictions for detector performance

EOS concept paper published: *JINST 18 P02009 (2023)*,
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/18/02/P02009>

EOS timeline

1. Detector construction (Sept. 2023 – Jan. 2024)

2. Cabling, electronics installation, DAQ commissioning, recirculation system installation, water fill (Jan. 2024 – Mar. 2024)

Custom trigger board

Custom front-end board

Ultra-fast EOS PMT

Water/WbLS recirculation system

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3. Water data collection for calibration (Mar. 2024 – Feb. 2025)

4. WbLS injection and data collection (ongoing, 2025)

WbLS at BNL

Challenges faced

Outer vessel and assembly stand, May '23

Challenges faced

Outer vessel and assembly stand, May '23

Shipping, June 1 '23

June 2, 2023

Tank install (Sept 14th)

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Upper PMT array (Oct 18th)

Inner vessel (Oct 25th)

IV unveiling, Barrel PMTs (early Nov)

First dichroicon install (Nov 13th)

Complete dichroicon install (Nov 17th)

Lower array connection (Nov 24th)

Detector lift (Jan 26th)

Detector lift (Jan 26th)

Detector lift (Jan 26th)

EOS: results & status

Precision timing

Excellent Data/MC agreement

EOS: results & status

Precision timing

Cherenkov ring imaging at 2MeV

Preliminary WbLS data

Excellent Data/MC agreement

Hybrid detector timeline

★ Eos project approval

\$450k LDRD

\$15M+ supported by DOE-NNSA-DNN R&D

\$2M+ supported by DOE-OHEP (via UCB)

Neutrinos for nonproliferation

Neutrino properties

Produced as a by-product of fission and fusion

Provide a unique signature of nuclear fission / fusion

Weakly interacting

Signature can't be shielded

Close to massless, travel $\sim c$

Near-instantaneous detection

Interaction products preserve incident direction

Can be used to "point" back to the source

- NuTools: 2021 study (DNN R&D) "exploring practical roles for neutrinos in nuclear energy and security"
- LBNL's focus is to advance the technology to enhance the capabilities of such a detector
- Reduce the required scale, increase standoff, and provide additional synergies with Office of Science interests
- Close partnership with related efforts at BNL & LLNL

Eos@SNS

- Unique physics program
 - * $\nu_e + {}^{130}\text{Te} \rightarrow {}^{130}\text{I} + e^-$
 - β -decay, Q-value 2.9MeV
 - Cross-section unknown
 - * CC $\nu_e {}^{16}\text{O}$ xsec
 - * BSM exotic searches
- First-of-kind technical demonstration
 - * CC / ES separation
- Near-surface neutrino detection, background reduction
- Existing detector, modest cost

The EOS team

Oak Ridge National Lab (2025)

- Team breakdown:**
- 3 national laboratories
 - 18 top-tier US institutions
 - 8 international collaborating institutions
 - 10 postdoctoral scholars
 - 9 graduate students
 - 18 undergraduate students

USA

Germany

Portugal

Finland

Canada

Summary

- EOS: technology demonstrator for next-gen neutrino detection
- Developed, constructed, operated with funding from DOE-NNSA-DNN-R&D
- Deployment of EOS to the SNS offers:
 - Rich physics program combining NP & HEP: cross sections, BSM
 - Nuclear non-proliferation relevant demonstration
 - Unique opportunity for technical demonstration of keystone THEIA concept (CC / ES separation)
- Directly informs development for THEIA

Acknowledgements

This work was performed under the auspices of the U.S. Department of Energy by Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory under Contract DE-AC02-05CHI1231. The project was funded by the U.S. Department of Energy, National Nuclear Security Administration, Office of Defense Nuclear Nonproliferation Research and Development (DNN R&D) (FY19, FY20-24). This material is based upon work supported by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science, Office of High Energy Physics, under Award Number DE-SC0018974 (FY18-20). This work was funded in-part by the Consortium for Monitoring, Technology, and Verification under Department of Energy National Nuclear Security Administration award number DE-NA0003920 (FY20-24), and the Nuclear Science and Security Consortium under Award Number DE-NA0003180 (FY19-20).

Thank you!

Non-comprehensive list of citations

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Backup

Eos Calibration Sources

Laserball

Isotropic light from picosecond laser
Four different wavelengths

AmBe

Coincidence (4.4 MeV γ , neutron)

Tagged cosmics

Michel e^- and neutron followers

Cherenkov

^{90}Sr source in UVT acrylic block

Directional

Directional e^- from either ^{90}Sr or ^{106}Ru sources

Thorium

Primarily 2.6 MeV γ -rays from thoriated rods

Photon detection

- Top PMT Array, quantity 26, 12 inch PMTs arranged in spherical pattern

- Barrel PMT Array, arranged in a cylindrical pattern
- Quantity 168 (7 X 24), 8 inch PMTs
- Simple unistrut hangers, sheet metal brackets similar to Daya Bay

- Bottom PMT Array, arranged in a spherical pattern
- 12x 10 inch PMTs behind dished head
- 36x 8 inch PMTs in front of dished head
- 12x dichroicons in front of 8 inch PMTs

PMT team

- Excellent team working on testing and assembling PMTs
 - **Lead:** Tanner Kaptanoglu (UC Berkeley)
 - **Undergraduates:**
 - Ashley Rincon (UC Berkeley)
 - Hong Joo Ryoo (UC Berkeley)
 - Joseph Koplowitz (UC Berkeley)
 - Sawyer Kaplan (UC Berkeley)
 - Skipper Lynch (MIT)
 - **Graduate Students:**
 - Mackenzie Duce (Georgia Tech – ETI)
 - Sam Naugle (U. Penn)
 - Ben Harris (U. Penn)
 - James Shen (U. Penn)
 - Adam Baldoni (Penn. State)
 - Garrett Wendel (Penn. State)
 - **Researchers:**
 - Zara Bagdasarian (UC Berkeley)
 - Leon Pickard (UC Berkeley)

Eos PMT team during 8” PMT assembly
(Z. Bagdasarian, A. Rincon, J. Koplowitz, S. Lynch, S. Kaplan)

PMT testing

Performance requirements (for a gain of 10^7):

- High voltage < 2500 V
- TTS (SE) < 1.4 ns
- Charge P/V (SPE) > 2
- Dark noise rate < 10 kHz
- Afterpulsing rate $< 15\%$

Dichroicons

Sort short wavelength (scintillation) and long-wavelength (Cherenkov) photons towards different PMTs using a parabolic concentrator built from dichroic filters

Dichroicon

8" PMT

10" PMT

Readout

Requirements

- Provide HV power and control to PMTs; decouple signal from HV
- (Triggered) digitization of waveforms for 242 photomultiplier channels
- Dynamic range from $< 1/4$ pe to 100 pe
- Timing precision better than PMT transit time jitter (~ 1 ns)
- Flexible triggering to accommodate calibration sources, cosmic rays, and geographic triggering (e.g., dichroicon-only triggers)
- Configuration, control, and monitoring at run time
- Event “building” and storage of triggered data to disk

6 main blocks

- PMT HV power: CAEN SY4527
- 17 waveform digitizers: CAEN v1730 (500 MS/s, 14 bit)
- DAQ server reads out digitizers over optical fiber
- 16 custom-designed HV splitter and summer (HVSS)
- 3 custom-designed Central Analog Summing Boards (CASB)
- 1 custom digital trigger system (Penn Trigger Board: PTB)

Source deployment

Calibration
deployment
arm

- Calibrations: understanding the detector
 - PMT timing, gain, efficiency
 - Scintillator properties (LY, time profile, attenuation)
- Reconstruction performance: project deliverables
 - Position, energy, direction

Source deployment

- Radioactive sources

- γ : ^{137}Cs , AmBe

- β : ^{90}Sr (2.3 MeV), ^{106}Ru (3.5MeV)

- Light injection system

- Fast pulsed diode laser (19ps)

- 375, 405, 440, 510nm

- Fibres: 1 central + 36 barrel

- Natural sources: μ , BiPos

- 500 Hz muons

- 20 Hz neutrons

- Several Hz Michels

- Modestly narrow beam of collimated electrons

- Self-triggering (scintillating fibres viewed by 2 SiPMs)

- Expect Hz-level rates of tagged events

Custom laser simulations

Source deployment

1. Cherenkov source: acrylic-encapsulated beta source

- Absolute light source: decouple light yield / collection
- Probe scintillator properties (emission vs re-emission)

2. Hot-Th source: thoriated tungsten welding rods

- Hot source to overcome background (surface deployment)
- Energy, position demonstration

Source design

10 Tungsten welding rods

4%-Thoriated

7" tall

Installation procedure

Assembly stands

Highly-instrumented detector:
20-ton outer vessel
4.1-ton inner vessel
242 channel count (of 4 kinds)
+ 24 optical fibres
+ 12 dichroicons
+ 72 muon-counter panels

3-year project period:
Design, procurement, testing,
integration, calibration & operation

Comparable scale projects:

- Double Chooz ($\sim x2$):
reactor neutrino detection
- Outer detector of LZ (OHEP)
- Photon detection system of
SBND (Short Baseline Neutrino
Detector)
- ANNIE

<https://inspirehep.net/literature/2022838>

Installation procedure

EOS @ SNS (ORNL)

- SNS provides both neutrinos and anti neutrinos
- Detection of Inverse Beta Decay: relevant for reactors
- Detection of Elastic Scattering events: directionality “holy grail”
- Neutron studies: evaluate background rejection
- Possible space identified at ORNL
- Additional technology development opportunity:
 - ▶ Li-loaded WbLS (5% organic, 10% Li)
 - ▶ Enhanced ν_e detection : CC on ${}^7\text{Li}$, spectral precision
- Supernova-relevant demonstration
- Beyond-SM searches

Channel	Rate at 20m Standoff (ev/yr)
$\nu_e e$ ES	136.89
$\nu_\mu e$ ES	20.89
$\bar{\nu}_\mu e$ ES	22.48
ν_e - ${}^7\text{Li}$ CC	533.30
ν_e - ${}^{16}\text{O}$ CC	459.34
ν_e - ${}^{12}\text{C}$ CC	37.08

event rates expected for 4 tons of LiWbLS

ν flux at SNS

neutrino cross-sections in LiWbLS

possible site for EOS deployment

Potential impact (nonpro)

Benefits of hybrid technology

- Scalable to large (10s kton) scales
 - Ability to monitor at large standoff distance
 - Sensitivity to weak signals
 - High-fidelity event reconstruction and particle identification
 - High signal efficiency
 - Powerful background rejection
- ➔ Good signal-to-noise ratio, improved sensitivity

Benefits of Eos deployment

- Evaluate event reconstruction capabilities
 - *Future: evaluate particle identification and background rejection capabilities*
 - *Future: measure background rates at / near surface*
 - *Future: direct neutrino detection from a source*
- ➔ Demonstrate potential for surface deployment
- ➔ Cost driver for any future application

Potential impact (science)

